

ECONOMICS

DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY - CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

Zhozhushvili N.

Doctor of Economic sciences

Associate Professor of Gori State University

Abstract

In 2020 and 2021, the pandemic processes of COVID-19 in many countries of the world led to an increase in the pace of technological changes and prompted the emergence of digital entrepreneurship to solve various challenges. To date, the pace of technological development in the modern world is increasing. An organization that cannot manage this process will not be able to meet the minimum requirements of the market, will fall behind, and will not be able to withstand the competition. Both the Georgian business sector and the state are actively involved in these processes, although they face many challenges. It is very important to implement targeted support programs, Internet access, develop financial support mechanisms, and improve digital skills and literacy to achieve digital transformation in entrepreneurship in dynamically developing countries.

Keywords: digitalization, transformation, challenges, digital entrepreneurship, risks.

Introduction

Being an entrepreneur includes an all-inclusive list of activities and innovations - from creating something new, or improving an already existing product, to inventing a high-tech innovation. The creation of different digital platforms and therefore, large-scale usage of the Internet contributed to the formation of a modern form of entrepreneurial activity - digital entrepreneurship. Lots of different digital products are created through this innovative activity, such as mobile applications, video games, online platforms, and so on. Through technology integration, team management, employee information storage, project management - physical storage of each document, agreement, communication with potential and existing customers without any barriers and marketing are done. Digital entrepreneurship involves innovative activities through which a digital product is created.

For starting a digital entrepreneurship, it is important to have a progressive outlook on the modern technological and electronic market situation, the development of entrepreneurial and digital innovations, the ability to predict future trends, and a sense of creativity. The COVID-19 crisis in business has accelerated the digitization of customer interactions. The need to create a digital business. Digital business is a new business arrangement where the digital and physical worlds merge, using digital tools - the Internet, digital data, or software. Changes applied to all business and public organizations, as well as people's personal lives. Society has had to keep up with the accelerated digital transformation processes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

During the Covid-19 pandemic process of digital transformation has been very accelerated, because the public and private sectors have had to work remotely to perform their tasks and functions. Despite the positive sides of digital transformation, during its' development phase, there were a lot of challenges. It was especially noticeable for developing countries' economy, for example - Georgia's situation. The purpose of this research was finding out the importance of digital trans-

formation in business process management and maintaining the competitiveness of enterprises, studying and analyzing the main challenges that accompany digital processes in the management process.

After the pandemic, the process of digitization in small and medium-sized enterprises began in many countries of the world. **The aim of the paper** is to highlight the main challenges facing developing countries in the direction of promoting the development of digital entrepreneurship.

For this purpose, the following methods are used in the paper, such as desk research methods (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, or other techniques) as well as statistical methods (grouping, graphical or tabular representation, and others). A survey of question-and-answer methods was also done, as well as quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Literature Review

The results of researches and guidelines related to digital business are used in this paper. The literature includes English-language studies, official websites of existing enterprises that carry out digitization of business processes.

1. Mariusz Soltanifar, Mathew Hughes, Lutz Göcke. 2021. „ Digital Entrepreneurship Impact on Business and Society’’ This book contains contributions by a group of scholars, university professors, researchers, entrepreneurs and managers whose expertise in their given areas offers valuable insights into the theme of digital entrepreneurship. In addition to the editorial work provided by the editors and authors, multiple cases have been consulted, redeveloped or written alongside the companies' representatives. Each chapter follows a general structure, introducing the significance and importance of its theme to scholars and practitioners, followed by an explanation of the content grounded in scholarly research. From there, the chapters present a conceptual framework that can be used as a tool by practitioners, followed by a series of case studies illustrating their application. Each chapter then draws conclusions with insights for practitioners. We trust you will find new knowledge, ideas and inspirations about

digital entrepreneurship through the course of this book.

2. Rabi'ah Seman | Rusmaini Ramly. 2022. „Digital Entrepreneurship”. his book functions as an additional reference sources for students who enroll in the Digital Entrepreneurship course or who may find the content relevant to their interest. The uniqueness of this book is displayed in the form of easy-to-understand text in a compact form to make it easier for students and readers to make references. The book is illustrated with pictures related to the topic discussed, with aims to ensure that students can relate to the real situation.

3. Fostering Business Development and Digitalisation in Georgia with cover. 2022. Over the past years, the Government of Georgia has made significant political efforts to create a favorable environment for private sector development and entrepreneurship, in particular to support small and medium-sized enterprises. The OECD supports these reforms and works closely with the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development (MoESD) to identify existing gaps and develop appropriate measures to create a favorable policy environment for Georgian SMEs. Georgia participated Little Eastern Partnership countries business regulator In three rounds of legislation evaluation, it was named as the country with the best results in this regard. The results of these assessments were reflected in the relevant OECD publications - SME Policy Index: Eastern Partnership Countries 2012, 2016 and 2020.

Main part

„Digital transformation is an approach, where with the use of information and technology in a secure environment transforms business elements so that your company is aligned with the challenges of the modern market and gains a competitive advantage.“ [1]

Every initiative of digital transformation has its goal. To begin with, it is expressed and reflected in the improvement of the current processes of the company. Digital transformation is inevitable for companies, in order for them to maintain competitiveness. The term "digitalization" is used to explain digitization, which is considered one of the most trending terms, both in the business sector, as well as in public and academic circles. A certain part of society considers digitalization to be the influence of digital communication and media on modern life, and according to the global research and consulting company Gartner's dictionary of information technology terms - "Digitalization refers to the change of the business model using digital technologies and the emergence of new sources of income or the creation of new values/opportunities. This is the process of digitizing the business." Digital transformations differ from conventional business transformations in both small and large ways. First, business transformations usually end after new behavior is achieved. Digital transformations, on the other hand, are a long-term effort to rethink how an organization is constantly improving and changing. This is because technology is not only being integrated into business, but is constantly evolving. For example, given the growing importance of artificial intelligence in business idea generation and decision making, any digital transformation must also be an AI transformation.

Pervasive digitalisation leads not only to spotting emerging opportunities in the digital environment, but also, more importantly, to prioritising them over other possible products. Implementing a digital mindset should result in a business recognising and exploiting opportunities arising from phenomena such as:

1. Technological developments and advances in infrastructure
2. Artificial intelligence used to enhance the quality of decisions
3. Augmented reality used to broaden entrepreneurs' horizons
4. Cloud services
5. Borderless connections in exploiting emerging opportunities

6. The sale of digital products or services across electronic networks Fundamentally, many digital technologies provide possibilities for efficiency [11, p.7 – 8] gains and customer intimacy. However, if people lack the right mindset to implement change and the current organisational practices are flawed, digital transformation will simply magnify the existing flaws.

AI is one of the forms of digital transformation. There are many definitions of artificial intelligence, but to put it simply, it is a flexible computer system made of algorithms, which, through the analysis of existing data and experience, has the ability to take a certain action independently of a person, to make a decision in a specific situation, whether it is an automated process that has already been repeated many times or a new case. The quality of the mechanism created using artificial intelligence is measured by the complexity of the tasks it has to solve. Comprehensive digitalization leads not only to the discovery of emerging opportunities in the digital environment, but also, more importantly, to their priority over other possible products. The implementation of digital thinking should lead to business recognition and utilization of opportunities arising from phenomena such as - technological developments and advances in infrastructure, artificial intelligence used to improve the quality of decisions, augmented reality used to expand the horizons of entrepreneurs, cloud services, limitless connections in the use of emerging opportunities, selling digital products or services in electronic networks mainly, many digital technologies provide opportunities for efficiency. Profitability and personal customer relations. But if people do not have correct ways of thinking and viewing things in order to implement changes and existing organizational practices are flawed, digital transformation will simply increase existing flaws. [9]

European Union made two main goals for 2030 for digital transformation business. First, more than 90% of SMEs should reach at least a basic level of digital intensity, and 75% of EU companies should use cloud computing services, perform data analysis or use artificial intelligence. The digital intensity of businesses is monitored by the Digital Intensity Index (DII), which measures businesses' use of 12 different digital technologies. The index ranks businesses based on how much digital technology they use: "0-3" - very low, "4-6" -

low, "7-9" - high, "10-12" - very high. Almost 70% of EU SMEs achieve basic digital intensity. In 2022, 70% of all EU businesses will have reached a baseline level of digital intensity. The share of small and medium-sized businesses was 69%, and for large businesses - 98%. The share of SMEs with a baseline level of digital intensity ranged from 41% in Greece and 47% in Bulgaria to 89% in Denmark and 90% in Finland. One in five businesses in the EU are training their staff to develop ICT skills. Digital skills can be acquired in different settings, for example in schools, privately or at work. Businesses can play an important role in improving the ICT skills of their staff. In 2022, 22% of EU businesses provided training to staff to develop or improve their ICT skills. Finland (40%), Sweden (34%), Denmark and Belgium (both 33%) lead the EU with the highest share of enterprises providing ICT training for their staff. When looking at business size, this share reached 70% for large businesses, compared to 21% for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). [2]

The modern world, where businesses operate today, is digital. Which automatically hints to companies to go digital too. The companies think of ways of "how to go digital effectively", which is an important step for the development of the company. The transformation to going digital changes how the company operates, and affects its' work process, communication channels, organizational structure, and culture. The range of applications of digital technologies is wide, and the benefits obtained from their use are very diverse. The digital revolution created a new way of connecting people, processes, and technologies to each other. It allows companies and their users to find a common language in one space. Digital transformation is a new way of solving problems - it adds new value to companies. Digital transformation is a continuous process that makes companies ready to meet new challenges. BDO Digital listed 7 main business elements, of which transformation is necessary for the digital transformation process. These elements are: Data, processes, customers, technology, culture and employees, sales channels and cyber security. [1] Digitization can bring significant benefits to economies and societies. Especially it helps small and medium-sized businesses to increase productivity in facilitating access to strategic resources by expanding customer base and market access, increasing scale, and capitalizing on network effects.

Digital business can be understood as an activity, which uses digital technologies to create new values in business models, customer experiences, and internal capabilities. Digital business changes the ways organizations view technology. This mindset is directed towards innovation, revenue, and market growth. Digital business focuses more on how technology enables companies to create new values and experiences that differentiate companies from each other and gives them a competitive advantage.

There are three Online Business Model:

Retail

- Traditional/standard model
- Generate profit by selling to the customer at a markup cost

Affiliate

- A company generate profit by engaging other company/individuals as middleman (affiliates)
- Affiliates promote product by putting advertisement / link to the business via their website / social media;

- Affiliates earn commission

Dropship

- Seller do not keep stocks/inventories
- Seller promote and get order
- Product will be delivered by the dropshipping provider

But they have special risks and issues: Cyber Security, Online Scams, Safety Precautions, Digital Security; [10, p.52 – 59]

In the modern world, we are often met with terms such as e-commerce. E-commerce refers to a business that electronically manages both product and/or service collections and payments. Through e-commerce actions are aimed at buying or selling products through online services or the Internet. Often times, there is confusion between two terms: e-commerce and e-business. But there is a very important difference between these two. E-business is a broader concept and it includes complex processes for managing an online business, including e-commerce, which involves the selling of a product/service directly between a seller and a buyer. [7, p.8 – 9]

The size of Georgia's e-commerce market grew to 138 million GEL (about \$44 million) in 2020, with many firms forced to shift their operations online due to lockdowns and social distancing measures. [4] As for the demand perspective, the share of Georgians aged 15 and over who use the Internet for online shopping increased by 15% between 2016 and 2020 (+50% among 15-29-year-olds), however, there is still huge potential for growth. [5] In 2018, the Ministry developed a draft law on e-commerce, which should comply with the EU e-commerce directive and DCFTA requirements. This new law should define the rights and obligations of operators of intermediary service providers, strengthen customer protection, and increase the reliability of services for both small and medium-sized businesses and consumers.

Over the past years, the Government of Georgia has made significant political efforts to support small and medium-sized enterprises. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) supports these efforts and works closely with the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development (MoESD) to develop appropriate measures to create a favorable policy environment for Georgian small and medium-sized businesses. OECD assisted Georgia in the preparation of a new small and medium-sized entrepreneurship development strategy. (Strategy 2021-2025). The OECD

is helping the Government of Georgia to develop appropriate policies to accelerate the digital transformation of small and medium-sized businesses. A document showing the results of the evaluation was drafted by the partner organizations, where an important part is dedicated to the digitization of small and medium-sized businesses in Georgia. It overlooks the current situation in terms of special support programs for the digitization of small and medium-sized businesses. In the past few years, there have been created quite a few fast-growing digital startups, such as b2c.ge, firm, which is helping other businesses to open up their online stores.

The COVID-19 crisis has greatly accelerated digital transformation. Since governments, businesses, and individuals have been forced to work remotely, they have had to increase the share of tasks performed using online platforms. The country's periodic lockdowns and long-term social distancing measures have led to a

sharp decline in mobility: use of public transport hubs fell to 78% compared to April 2020, and workplace reporting fell to 81%. By the fall of 2020, more than a third of Georgian firms have started or increased their online business activities and the number of visits to online stores has tripled between 2019 and 2021, reflecting changes in consumer habits that are likely to persist. [6] Similarly, Georgians have significantly increased their use of e-government services: while the government almost doubled the number of services available on the my.gov.ge portal, reaching 700 in 2020, the use of these services increased more than 9 times. The impact of COVID-19 on business online activity by firm size. Percentage of firms that have initiated or increased online business activity in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. [3, p.81] (Table 1)

Table 1.

Note: R-1 corresponds to the results of a follow-up study conducted in June 2020, R-2 to the results of a study conducted in October/November 2020. [13]

Conclusions

Only a few Georgian companies offering AI services to traditional businesses have emerged in Georgia: for example, fintech startup Optio.AI enables financial firms to categorize customer transactions and provides business-tailored advice on cost optimization through an AI-powered chatbot. The firm recently partnered with the Bank of Georgia to hire a virtual assistant. [9]

In Georgia, large firms are twice as likely to implement and use online tools to receive and process orders than smaller firms but are about four times more likely to use new technologies. These digital divides hinder economic growth and create the risk of widening inequality, as the delay in digitization of small and medium-sized businesses prevents them from reaping the benefits that the introduction of digital tools offers, further widening the existing gap in terms of productivity.

Georgia is involved in several regional and international initiatives aimed at improving broadband telecommunications infrastructure, speed, and availability. The creation of a digital telecommunications corridor, which will provide a modern transit fiber optic infrastructure network, will be considered, connecting Europe to Asia through Georgia, Armenia, and Azerbaijan. Any step taken by the state to promote business digitization is an important support for the business sector, which is a precursor to the strengthening of the economy and the well-being of society. It is very important to implement targeted support programs, Internet access, develop financial support mechanisms, and improve digital skills and literacy to achieve digital transformation in entrepreneurship in dynamically developing countries.

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